

Integrated vibration-based bridge monitoring approach for freight dominated lines

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ABSTRACT: The Iron Ore Line, a freight-dominated corridor, plays a vital role in transport between Sweden and Norway. Enhancing the corridor's reliability requires attention to key infrastructure such as bridges, which are subjected to high dynamic loads from heavy haul traffic operating at a maximum axle load of 32.5 tons. This study presents a monitoring framework for railway bridges and their associated transition zones using an integrated approach that combines onboard Axle Box Acceleration (ABA) measurements, falling weight impact tests, and measurements of bridge responses during train passages (pass-by measurements). A field measurement campaign was conducted on a single-span bridge and its transition zones along the Iron Ore Line. We demonstrate that the characteristic frequencies and their spatial variations derived from ABA data can be used for (a) evaluating track stiffness at transition zones and (b) identifying the bridge's natural frequencies and their spatial variations, which can be further used for location-specific bridge condition monitoring. The ABA results are validated by the falling weight and pass-by measurements. These findings support ABA's potential as a scalable tool for large-scale bridge condition monitoring.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Iron Ore Line is a freight-dominated corridor connecting Kiruna in northern Sweden to the ports of Narvik in Norway and Luleå in Sweden. Built in the early 1900s and extending approximately 500 km, this corridor plays a critical economic role in transporting millions of tons of iron ore annually. Over the decades, the axle load capacity has progressively increased, from 14 tons at its inception to 32.5 tons in 2017 (Coric et al., 2018) to meet growing freight demands.

Given the strategic and economic importance of the line, any disruption can result in substantial financial loss. For instance, a derailment near Vassijaure in December 2023 halted operations for nearly two months, with estimated daily losses of around 100

million SEK (\approx 10 million USD) due to shipment delays and operational downtime (High North News, 2025).

The progressive increase in axle loads has elevated dynamic forces acting on the railway infrastructure, especially on bridges. Over time, these repeated loads contribute to structural degradation, making bridges a potential source of unforeseen disruptions. Therefore, ensuring the resilience of such critical infrastructure requires proactive monitoring solutions that can detect emerging weaknesses before they lead to failure.

Current bridge monitoring predominantly relies on trackside inspections and fixed instrumentation, which are costly to deploy and maintain. Over 35% of railway bridges in Europe are more than a hundred years old and require monitoring (Vagnoli et al.,

2018). In practice, monitoring campaigns often involve complex sensor networks (Chan et al., 2006; Feng and Feng, 2015; Orbán and Gutermann, 2009; Vagnoli et al., 2018) that are not only expensive but also difficult to interpret, limiting their scalability across large railway networks. As a more scalable alternative, onboard monitoring utilizes data collected during regular train operations (Bragança et al., 2023; de Souza et al., 2024). However, onboard measurements alone may lack the contextual information needed for reliable interpretation.

In response, this paper presents an integrated vibration-based monitoring approach for railway bridges, combining: (i) onboard Axle Box Acceleration (ABA) to capture train-track-bridge interactions, (ii) impact tests using a falling weight to assess the dynamic behavior of the track-bridge system under controlled excitation, and (iii) bridge response measurements during operational train loads. By linking these complementary methods, the study aims to demonstrate that ABA can serve as a scalable tool for large-scale bridge condition monitoring, ultimately helping to prevent costly derailments and enhance infrastructure resilience in railway operations.

2 METHODOLOGY AND FIELD MEASUREMENT CAMPAIGN

2.1 Site description

The monitored bridge is located between Boden and Murjek stations on the Iron Ore Line in northern Sweden. It is a single-span structure accommodating a single ballasted track and is representative of typical bridge configurations under heavy-haul traffic on this corridor. The bridge is 8.15 meters in total length and comprises a 4.2-meter central span (bridge deck), flanked by a 1.9-meter approach slab on the north side and a 2.05-meter approach slab on the south side. The approach slabs serve as transition structures between the embankment and the main bridge span.

The superstructure consists of a reinforced concrete deck. Structural deterioration has been observed at the abutments in the form of visible cracks. To enhance structural support, two steel beams, spaced 2.6 meters apart, were installed beneath the bridge deck, as shown in Figure 1 (Unsiwilai et al., 2024). The steel beams were installed beneath the bridge deck without altering the original 4.2-meter span length. These beams provide additional load-bearing capacity to the existing structure. The bridge currently accommodates heavy haul traffic with maximum axle loads of 32.5 tons.

Detailed structural specifications, including foundation type and original design capacity, were not

available for this study. The bridge assessment presented here is based on field observations and dynamic measurements collected during the measurement campaign.

Trackside sensors were installed at significant locations to capture the dynamic response of the bridge under both operational and controlled loading conditions. Five accelerometers, called B-1 to B-5, were placed on the bridge deck and both approach slabs. This configuration was designed to monitor spatial variations in vertical acceleration.

Figure 1. An instrumented bridge and accelerometer locations

2.2 Onboard axle box acceleration (ABA) measurement

Vertical axle box accelerations were measured using unidirectional sensors mounted on all eight wheels of an instrumented passenger wagon, as shown in Figure 2. The onboard system also included a high-precision GPS and a data acquisition unit that sampled at a rate of 25.6 kHz. The collected signals were synchronized and converted from the time domain to the spatial domain for consistent location-based analysis. Wavelet-based methods were used to analyze the data, which captures spatial-frequency variations in dynamic response across the bridge.

Figure 2. ABA measurement system

2.3 Falling weight impact test

Falling weight tests were conducted to excite the track-bridge system with controlled impact forces and

record its dynamic response. A custom-designed apparatus, as shown in Figure 3, dropped stacked weights from various heights above the left rail head. An impact force was applied to the track-bridge system via a flat plastic tip at the rail head, positioned above the edge of the north approach slab near sensor B-1.

The impact force was measured using a load cell, while the structural response was captured by accelerometers and recorded using a data acquisition system at a sampling rate of 25.6 kHz. Multiple impact configurations enabled the computation of average Frequency Response Functions (FRF) at each sensor location.

Figure 3. The falling weight apparatus

2.4 Bridge response under train passages

Bridge vibrations were recorded during train passages (i.e., pass-by measurements) to capture dynamic responses under varying operational conditions. The measurements included several train runs with varying axle loads and travel directions, allowing an analysis of how the bridge responds to different loading setups.

3 RESULTS

This section presents findings from the integrated measurement campaign, which collectively aims to evaluate the effectiveness of onboard ABA measurements in characterizing bridge behavior.

3.1 ABA signal characteristics at the bridge

Vertical ABA signals recorded at the left rail during the instrumented wagon's passage over the bridge in the direction of Murjek at 31.7 m/s are presented as an example. The averaged ABA signal in the spatial

domain from the four left wheels is shown in Figure 4(a), while its synchrosqueezed wavelet transform spectrum, which depicts the signal in the spatial-frequency domain, is shown in Figure 4(b). Four bands of dominant frequency have been identified as follows:

- f_1 ranges from approximately 40 Hz at the normal track section to 70 Hz at the bridge deck.
- f_2 occurs near the south approach slab at around 30 Hz.
- f_3 varies from 18 Hz at the north approach slab to 14 Hz at the south approach slab.
- f_4 is approximately 7 Hz, which corresponds to the vehicle passing frequency over the bridge, i.e., $f_4 = v/L$, where v is the vehicle speed and L is the bridge span.

Figure 4. ABA signal: (a) in the spatial domain; (b) in the spatial-frequency domain

3.2 Transition zone

f_1 is related to the full track resonance, for which the wheel and track vibrate together on the track support stiffness. Therefore, the variations of f_1 were used to evaluate ballast stiffness variations, which were validated using field hammer tests (Shen et al., 2025; Unsiwilai et al., 2024).

The ballast stiffness in the transition zone reaches its maximum at around -2 m and then gradually decreases towards the bridge (0 m). This suggests that the sleepers near the bridge receive less support from the ballast.

3.3 Bridge dynamics

In the ABA signal (Figure 4(b)), three frequencies at approximately 70 Hz (f_1), 30 Hz (f_2), and 15 Hz (f_3) are unique at the bridge location and therefore related to bridge dynamics. In this section, we show that they correspond to the bridge resonances, which can be captured by the falling weight and pass-by measurements.

3.3.1 Falling weight tests

Figure 5 shows the frequency response functions (FRF) measured at the middle of the bridge deck (sensor B-3 in Figure 1). Three natural frequencies of the bridge can be observed, which match the three frequency bands ($f_1 \sim f_3$) in the ABA signal. The corresponding vibration modes are approximately the first, second, and third order bending modes of the bridge, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. FRFs of the bridge deck measured at location B-3

Figure 6. Operational deflection shapes (ODS) of the bridge, measured from B-1 to B-5

3.3.2 Pass-by measurements

Figure 7 shows the wavelet transforms of the signals (1.2 seconds) measured at sensors B-1 to B-5 during

the passage of iron ore wagons. The left column shows the scalograms, while the right column shows the time-averaged wavelet power over the measurement period. Three dominant frequency bands below 100 Hz are observed in the signals:

- f_1 increases from approximately 65 Hz at both approach slabs (B-1 and B-5) to around 80 Hz at the middle of the bridge deck (B-3).
- f_2 only appears at the south approach slab (B-4 and B-5) at around 24 Hz.
- f_3 decreases from 17.6 Hz at the north approach slab (B-1) to 13.4 Hz (B-5) at the south approach slab.

These three frequency bands and their spatial variations are consistent with the patterns identified in the ABA signals (see Section 3.1).

Figure 7. Scalograms (left column) and time-averaged wavelet power (right column) for the pass-by measurements at sensor locations B-1 to B-5. f_3 is also indicated by the dashed rectangles in the scalograms of B-4 and B-5 for clarity

4 DISCUSSION

The integrated monitoring framework presented in this study demonstrates the feasibility of using onboard ABA measurements for bridge condition assessment through the identification of characteristic frequencies and their spatial variations. Cross-validation with falling weight impact tests and pass-by measurements confirms that ABA-derived frequency

bands correspond to physical structural responses, establishing a foundation for vibration-based monitoring.

The wavelet-based analysis of ABA data captures spatial variations in dynamic behavior across different structural elements. For track-related components, frequency band f_1 has been shown to correlate with ballast stiffness variations at transition zones (Unsiwilai et al., 2024), providing a quantitative indicator for evaluating support conditions. The observed frequency variations across the bridge structure, specifically the spatial evolution of f_1 , f_2 , and f_3 , reflect the dynamic response of the track-bridge system under operational loading. While these frequencies can be detected and monitored, their connection to specific bridge structural conditions requires further investigation.

The interpretation of frequency changes in relation to specific structural degradation mechanisms remains a developing area of investigation. While the methodology can identify deviations from a baseline state, linking specific frequency changes to particular defect types requires data from multiple bridges with known structural conditions. Such databases would enable the development of diagnostic frameworks capable of distinguishing between various degradation scenarios, including foundation settlement, progressive cracking, or other forms of structural degradation.

5 CONCLUSION

This study presents an integrated approach for monitoring railway bridges and transition zones using onboard ABA, falling weight impact tests, and pass-by measurements. Results demonstrate that characteristic frequencies derived from ABA data effectively capture

Track stiffness variations at transition zones.

Natural frequencies and their spatial variations of the bridge.

These ABA-derived features were validated through falling weight and pass-by measurements, demonstrating agreement with the bridge's natural frequencies and spatial variation patterns observed under both controlled and operational loading. Such physical interpretability is critical for reliable condition monitoring, as it allows the identification of structural changes over space and time, such as stiffness degradation or natural frequency shifts, based on routinely collected onboard data. These findings support ABA's potential as a scalable, cost-effective tool for continuous, network-wide bridge condition monitoring.

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